

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Chemical Composition of the Essential Oil of Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) Seeds Harvested in Senegal

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 17-08-2022

Accepted: 30-11-2022

Published: 14-01-2023

Citation: Diedhiou D, Faye M, Candy L, Vandebossche V, Raynaud C, Sock O, Rigal L (2023) Chemical Composition of the Essential Oil of Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) Seeds Harvested in Senegal. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 16(2): 118-122. [http://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i2.1650](https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i2.1650)

* **Corresponding author.**djidied@hotmail.com**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

Copyright: © 2023 Diedhiou et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Djibril Diedhiou^{1,2,3*}, Mamadou Faye^{1,2}, Laure Candy²,
Virginie Vandebossche², Christine Raynaud², Oumar Sock¹, Luc Rigal²

1 Laboratoire Eau, Energie, Environnement et Procédés Industriels (LE3PI), ESP, UCAD, Dakar-Fann, 5085, Sénégal

2 Laboratoire de Chimie Agro-Industrielle (LCA), ENSIACET, INPT - 4, Allée Emile Monso, 44362 -31030, Toulouse Cedex, France

3 UFR Sciences Fondamentales et de l'Ingénieur /Université du Sine Saloum El Hadji Ibrahima Niass (USSEIN), Kaolack, Sénégal

Abstract

Objective: To make better understanding of the neem seed composition (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) particularly in Senegal by the extraction, the proportioning and the determination of the composition of its essential oil.

Methods: The extraction of essential oil from neem seeds is carried out by hydro-distillation. The Gas Chromatography (GC) and Mass Spectrometry (MS) were used for analysis and identification of components. **Findings:** The yield of essential oil from dry neem seeds (95.7% dry matter) is 0.076%. The major compounds identified are 5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl- (4H) 1-3,5-dithiazine (39.1%), cis 1,2,4-Trithiolane, 3, 5-diethyl (7.9%), 1-H-indole 2,3-dione (7.9%), trans 1,2,4-Trithiolane, 3,5-diethyl (6.2%), and ethyl thioisobutyrate (4%). The classification of compounds reveals that the essential oil of neem seeds is composed of sulfur and nitrogen compounds (40.1%), sulfur compounds (25.3%), and nitrogen compounds (15.1%), sesquiterpenes (7.4%), Fatty Acid Esters (FAE) (1.5%) and hydrocarbons (0.4%). This composition reveals that neem essential oil is mainly composed of non-terpene compounds. **Novelty:** The method of analysis by GC-MS although being the most widely implemented in the quantification and identification of volatile compounds is not applied in the case of neem seeds of African origin.

Keywords: Chemical Composition; Essential Oil; Neem; *Azadirachta indica*; Seeds

1 Introduction

Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) is a plant of the Meliaceae family. It originates from the Indian subcontinent. This plant is introduced in many tropical countries such as Senegal. Different parts or extracts of the plant (fruits, leaves, roots, bark, oil, etc.) are used in traditional medicine, in the treatment of many diseases⁽¹⁻⁷⁾. Indeed,

neem extracts have many biological activities such as antibacterial, fungicidal, broad-spectrum of insecticidal, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, anticancer and hypoglycemic^(8–12). The oil is used in cosmetics in the manufacturing of toilet soaps, anti-dandruff shampoos⁽²⁾, surfactant oil for hospital textiles⁽¹³⁾ and in the production of biofuel^(14,15). Despite the many works dealt with to characterize neem seeds and to guide the valuation of their constituents, the essential oil of these seeds is still unknown. In particular, that of neem seeds from West Africa, particularly in Senegal, has not yet been the subject of study, despite the interest it could have. The extraction of essential oils from plant materials is generally done by hydrodistillation because of its efficiency. For the determination of the composition, the most widely used method is that of Gas Chromatography (GC) analysis coupled with Mass Spectrometry (MS).

This study aims to determine the content using the method of extraction by hydrodistillation and the composition of the essential oil of neem seeds analysis GC-MS.

2 Methodology

2.1 Biological material

The mature and dry neem seeds studied were collected in southern Senegal, dried at sunlight and then in an oven at 40 °C for 7 days. The grinding of these seeds is carried out using an Ika Werke MF 10 basic type knife mill, fitted with a sieve with a 1 mm mesh. And the Dry Matter (DM) content is determined according to the French standard NF V 03-603.

2.2 Extraction of essential oil

The extraction of essential oil from neem seeds is carried out by hydro-distillation. 100 g of seeds are crushed using a blade mill and introduced into the flask of the hydro-distiller containing 1 L of water. After boiling the medium during 6 hours, essential oil obtained is recovered with pentane and then dried by a stream of nitrogen gas according to the method recommended by the French pharmacopoeia.

2.3 Analysis of essential oil

The analysis is carried out by Gas Chromatography (GC) using a VARIAN STAR GC FID HP 5890 chromatograph equipped with a 5m nonpolar VF column (30 m × 0.32 mm and a 1 μm film). The temperature of the column is programmed from 40 °C to 280 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min for a total duration of 48 min. The carrier gas consists of helium with a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min by injection split. A volume of 0.5 μL is injected at a temperature of 200 °C and pressure at the top of the column maintained at 15 psi. Quantification is performed by FID at 280 °C. The identification of the compounds is carried out by Mass Spectrometry (MS) type AGILENT 5973 under the same analysis conditions as in GC.

3 Results and Discussion

The yield of essential oil from neem seeds, from hydro-distillation after six (6) hours, is equal to 0.076%. This content is higher than that of the essential oil of neem seeds collected in India (0.028%)⁽¹⁶⁾.

This relatively low essential oil content of neem seeds collected in Senegal is higher than those of certain essential oil of certain seeds such as those of longose, *Alpinia zerumbet* (0.04%)⁽¹⁷⁾ but lower than that of other seeds such as common coriander, *Coriandrum sativum* (from 0.31 to 0.8%)^(18,19) or black cumin seeds, *Nigella sativa* (0.68 - 1.28)⁽²⁰⁾, Celery seeds, *Apium graveolens* (from 1,456 to 1,927%)⁽²¹⁾.

In total, 34 compounds have been identified by GC-MS method, a number of compounds greater than that of the essential oil of *Moringa oleifera* (24 compounds)⁽²²⁾ but lower than those of essential oils from *Zingiber roseum* seeds (47 compounds)⁽²³⁾, and Coriander (58 compounds)⁽¹⁹⁾.

The results of the analysis show that the major compound is 5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl- (4H) 1-3,5-dithiazine also called thialdine (39.1%). It is a heterocyclic compound, consisting of a cycle with 3 carbon atoms, 2 sulfur atoms and a nitrogen atom). Unlike the essential oil of neem seeds, characterized by the preponderance of a non-terpene molecule, other essential oils of seeds such as that of coriander seeds, mainly composed of linalool in very high proportion, from 49 to 52%⁽¹⁸⁾ or that of black cumin seed of which p-cymene (44.6 and 46%) is the major compound⁽¹⁹⁾.

The other compounds in significant proportion are the cis 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl (7.9%), the 1H-indole 2,3-dione (7.5%), the trans 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl (6.2%) and the ethyl thioisobutyrate (4%) (Table 1). Indeed, 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl and trans 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl are sulfur heterocycles. We can thus notice that the majority compounds of the essential oil of neem seeds are essentially sulfur heterocycles. The sulfur heterocycles are a high proportion (about 56%).

This composition is quite special which sets it apart from other essential oils.

The composition reveals that the essential oil of neem seeds consists essentially of non-terpene compounds (of the order of 92.5% of compounds identified) against only of the order of 7.5% for the terpenic compounds. This low proportion of terpene compounds in this essential oil is quite rare.

Among these terpene compounds, some are quite frequently found in essential seed oils, such as α -Cedrene⁽²⁴⁾, α -Longipinene^(24–27), β -Bisabolene^(24,28), δ -Cadinene^(24,29,30).

The classification of compounds into categories (Table 2) reveals the dominance of sulfur and nitrogen compounds (40.1%), sulfur compounds (25.3%) and nitrogen compounds, mainly volatile alkaloids (15.1%). These volatile compounds, mainly sulfur or nitrogen, are believed to be responsible for its strong and pungent odor. Terpene compounds are mainly represented by the group of sesquiterpenes (7.4%). The Fatty Acid Esters (FAE) (1.5%) and the hydrocarbons (0.4%) are in small proportions. The very large proportion of sulfur and nitrogen compounds is believed to be responsible for the unpleasant odor of neem oil and its essential oil. But note that the smell of the essential oil is much more pleasant than that of its lipids, in part probably due to the presence of terpene molecules such as italicene, α -bergamotene, valencene, β -bisabolene, commonly found in pleasant smelling essential oils.

This composition of the essential oil of senegalese neem seeds differs from that obtained by Kurose and Yatagai, 2005 on neem seeds collected in India (56 identified compounds) whose major compounds are hexadecanoic acid (34%), oleic acid (15.7%) and 5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl-(4H)1-3,5-dithiazine (11.7%)⁽¹⁶⁾. Besides 5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl-(4H)1-3,5-dithiazine, other non-terpene compounds (Cis 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl and Trans 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl) and terpene molecules (Italicene, β -Bisabolene, Valencene and Bergamotene) are also found in the essential oil of Indian neem seeds.

This difference in content and composition of between the essential oil of neem seeds collected in Senegal and that of neem seeds collected in India could be explained by the difference in climatic conditions (rainfall, temperature, sunshine, etc.), edaphic and tree genotypes, which are not the same in these two countries.

Table 1. Composition of the essential oil of neem seeds

Compounds	Content (%)	RI ^a	<i>T_h</i> RI	Identification
2-Methyl-1-D1-aziridine	0.3	665	690	MS, RI
Tiirane methyl	0.3	854	-	MS, RI
3,4-Dimethylthiophene	1.3	887	884	MS, RI
Thiophene, 2,5-dimethyl	0.4	914	884	MS, RI
Disulfide, dipropyl	0.2	1117	1119	MS, RI
Ethyl thioisobutyrate	4	1131	-	MS, RI
2-Methyl-2-ethyl-1,3-dithiolane	0.3	1153	1116	MS, RI
Benzene 1-methyl 2-(propylthio)	0.8	1256	1356	MS, RI
1,1,2-Tri (methylthio) ethene	0.8	1264	1256	MS, RI
N-Formyl-3-methyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine	0.3	1311	-	MS, RI
Ethane 1,1'-[[methylthio] methylene] bis (thio) bis	0.7	1321	1306	MS, RI
Unidentified	0.5	-	-	MS, RI
Unidentified	0.3	-	-	MS, RI
Unidentified	0.3	-	-	MS, RI
Trans 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl	6.2	1354	1344	MS, RI
Cis 1,2,4-Trithiolane-3,5-diethyl	7.9	1363	1373	MS, RI
β -cubebene	0.6	1387	1388	MS, RI
2-propanamide 1-propene-1(1-methoxy)	2.6	1397	-	MS, RI
1H-indole 2,3-dione	7.5	1408	1381	MS, RI
(\pm) 3,5-Diethyl-1,2,4-trithiolane	0.7	1424	1378	MS, RI
Unidentified	1.6	-	-	MS, RI
α -Cedrene	0.6	1432	1411	MS, RI
Unidentified	0.4	-	-	MS, RI
α -Bergamotene	0.5	1438	1435	MS, RI
α -Longipinene	0.7	1450	1403	MS, RI
Bicyclo [4.4.0] dec-1-en 2-isopropyl-5-methyl-9-methylene	0.4	1462	1503	MS, RI
Italicene	0.7	1478	1405	MS, RI
5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl-(4H)1-3,5-dithiazine	39.1	1498	-	MS, RI
Valencene	1.2	1507	1496	MS, RI
β -Bisabolene	1	1513	1509	MS, RI

Continued on next page

Table 1 continued

δ -Cadinene	0.5	1527	1523	MS, RI
6,10,11,11-Tetramethyl tricyclo [6.3.0 (2,3)] undec-1 (7)-ene	2	1533	-	MS, RI
3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione 2,4-dihydro-5-methyl	1	-	-	MS, RI
Trans 3-hexanedioic acid, bis (trimethylsilyl) ester	1.5	1613	1586	MS, RI
1,3,4-Trithiane 2,2,4,4,6,6-hexamethyl	1.4	1619	1547	MS, RI
2-isopropoxyphenyl N-methylcarbamate	2.1	1661	1598	MS, RI
α -cadinol	1.6	1669	1653	MS, RI
Hexanoic acid 4-(1-pyrrolidinylmethyl methyl ester)	1.6	1683	1561	MS, RI
4 (1H)-pyrimidinone 2-amino 6-(methylamino)	1	1774	1552	MS, RI
Total	94.9			

RI^a : MS Retention Indices; ThRI : theoretical Retention Index; RI : Retention Index ; MS : Mass Spectrometry

Table 2. Groups of compounds in the essential oil of neem seeds

Groups of compounds	%
Nitrogen and sulfur compounds	40.1
Sulfur compounds	25.3
Nitrogen compounds (volatile alkaloids)	15.1
Sesquiterpenes	7.4
Fatty Acid Ethers (FAE)	1.5
Hydrocarbons	0.4
Identified compounds	89.8

4 Conclusion

Novelty: This study, among others, shows that the essential oil from neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seeds collected in Senegal is composed mainly of non-terpene sulfur and nitrogen compounds (around 80.2%) and few terpene compounds, mainly sesquiterpenes (around 7.5%). This particular composition is different from that of the essential oil of neem seeds harvested in India whose proportion of fatty acids is much higher (more than 50% of the compounds). Note that in this essential oil of Indian seeds, the majority compound is hexadecanoic acid. The proportion of fatty acid ester (about 8%) is higher than that of Senegal but that of 5,6-dihydro-2,4,6-triethyl-(4H)1-3,5-dithiazine (11.68%) is lower than that of senegalese seeds.

Prospects: Valuations of the essential oil of neem seeds can be considered, but it will first be necessary to do the characterization of the essential oil content to assess the antioxidant activity and other biological properties (antimicrobial, antiseptic, etc.) of the neem seed oil.

Recommendations: It would also be important to expand the field of study to other parts of neem (leaves, flowers, roots and bark) and explore their value.

5 Acknowledgment

Department for Cooperation and Cultural Action (SCAC) of the Embassy of France at Dakar (Senegal).

References

- Shareef M, Akhtar MS. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and its potential for safeguarding health, prevention and treatment of diseases. *Matrix Science Medica*. 2018;2(1):04–08. Available from: <http://doi.org/10.26480/MSM.01.2018.04.08>.
- Ashgar HA, Abbas SQ, Arshad MK, Jabin A, Usman B, Aslam M, et al. Therapeutic Potential of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem)-A Comprehensive Review. *Scholars International Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*. 2022;5(3):47–64. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.36348/sijtc.2022.v05i03.001>.
- Baby AR, Freire TB, Marques GDA, Rijo P, Lima FV, De Carvalho JCM, et al. *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) as a Potential Natural Active for Dermocosmetic and Topical Products: A Narrative Review. *Cosmetics*. 2022;9(3):58. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cosmetics9030058>.
- Islas JF, Acosta E, G-Buentello Z, Delgado-Gallegos JL, Moreno-Treviño MG, Escalante BG, et al. An overview of *Neem* (*Azadirachta indica*) and its potential impact on health. *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2020;74:104171. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2020.104171>.
- Moga MA, Bălan A, Anastasiu CV, Dimienescu OG, Neculoiu CD, Gavriș C. An Overview on the Anticancer Activity of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) in Gynecological Cancers. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2018;19(12):3898. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30563141/>.

- 6) Zhu WFF, Cheng JXX, Su SZZ, Zhang CFF, Akihisa T, Manosroi J, et al. Limonoids and tricyclic diterpenoids from *Azadirachta indica* and their antitumor activities. *Bioorganic Chemistry*. 2020;100:103889. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32388432/>.
- 7) Rahmani AH, Almatroudi A, Alrumaihi F, Khan AA. Pharmacological and therapeutic potential of neem (*Azadirachta indica*). *Pharmacognosy Reviews*. 2018;12(24):250–250. Available from: https://www.phcogrev.com/sites/default/files/PhcogRev_2018_12_24_250.pdf.
- 8) Guchhait KC, Manna T, Barai M, Karmakar M, Nandi SK, Jana D, et al. Antibiofilm and anticancer activities of unripe and ripe *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seed extracts. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*. 2022;22(1):42. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-022-03513-4>.
- 9) Tofel KH, Nukenine EN, Stähler M, Adler C. Insecticidal efficacy of *Azadirachta indica* powders from sun and shade-dried seeds against *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Callosobruchus maculatus*. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*. 2015;3(1):100–108. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272090532>.
- 10) Assefa H, Dagnaw T. Studies on Antimicrobial Properties of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) Seed Oil. 2022. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.aavs/2022/10.2.244.252>.
- 11) Mohideen M, Abidin NSIZ, Idris MIH, Kamaruzaman NA. An Overview of Antibacterial and Antifungal Effects of *Azadirachta indica* Crude Extract: A Narrative Review. *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*. 2022;15(1):505–514. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.13005/bpj/2391>.
- 12) Wylie MR, Merrell DS. The Antimicrobial Potential of the Neem Tree *Azadirachta indica*. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022;13:891535. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.891535>.
- 13) Sá CSDA, Ladhchumanandasivam R, Rossi CG, Silva RKD, Camboim WDS, Zille A, et al. Characterization of a natural surfactant from an essential oil from neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) for textile industry applications. *Textile Research Journal*. 2022;92(15-16):2643–2650. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175211007518>.
- 14) Bakari H, Djomdi, Ruben ZF, Delattre C, Pierre G, Dubessay P, et al. Influence of Physicochemical Characteristics of Neem Seeds (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) on Biodiesel Production. *Biomolecules*. 2020;10:616. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10040616>.
- 15) Diedhiou D, Diatta ML, Faye M, Vilarem G, Sock O, Rigal L. Biodiesel production from neem seeds (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) oil by its base-catalyzed transesterification and its blending with diesel. *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*. 2015;5(10):13–19. Available from: <http://www.isca.in/rjcs/Archives/v5/i10/3.ISCA-RJCS-2015-129.pdf>.
- 16) Kurose K, Yatagai M. Components of the essential oils of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, *Azadirachta siamensis* Velton, and *Azadirachta excelsa* (Jack) Jacobs and their comparison. *Journal of Wood Science*. 2005;51(2):185–188. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10086-004-0640-4>.
- 17) Abdelnaser A, Elzaawely TD, Xuan, Koyama H, Tawata S. Antioxidant activity and contents of essential oil and phenolic compounds in flowers and seeds of *Alpinia zerumbet*. *Food Chemistry*. 2007;104:1648–1653. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0308814607002415>.
- 18) Pavlic B, Vidovic S, Vladic J, Radosavljevic R, Zekovic Z. Isolation of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) essential oil by green extractions versus traditional techniques. *Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. 2015;99:23–28. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2015.01.029>.
- 19) Ghazanfari N, Mortazavi SA, Yazdi FT, Mohammadi M. Microwave-assisted hydrodistillation extraction of essential oil from coriander seeds and evaluation of their composition, antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. *Heliyon*. 2020;6(9):e04893. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04893>.
- 20) Hosseini SS, Rezaadoost H, Nadjafi F, Asareh MH. Comparative essential oil composition and fatty acid profiling of some Iranian black cumin landraces. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2019;140:111628. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.111628>.
- 21) Zorga J, Kunicka-Styczyńska A, Gruska R, Śmigielski K. Ultrasound-Assisted Hydrodistillation of Essential Oil from Celery Seeds (*Apium graveolens* L.) and Its Biological and Aroma Profiles. *Molecules*. 2020;25(22):5322. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225322>.
- 22) Hussein MA, Gobba NA, MH EB. Composition, in vitro antioxidant and antitumor properties of essential oil from the seeds of *Moringa oleifera*. *International Journal of Pharma Sciences*. 2014;4(3):532–540. Available from: <http://ijps.aizeonpublishers.net/content/2014/3/ijps532-540.pdf>.
- 23) Prakash O, Kasana VK, Pant AK, Zafar A, Hore SK, Mathela CS. Phytochemical composition of essential oil from seeds of *Zingiber roseum* Rosc. and its antispasmodic activity in rat duodenum. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2006;106(3):344–347. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16510259/>.
- 24) Nguyen TTT, Nguyen AV, Diep TT, Doan NN, Nguyen TTT. Essential oil profiles of seeds, peels, and leaves obtained from *Limnocitrus littoralis* (Miq.) swingle species, in the Southcentral coast of Vietnam. *All Life*. 2022;15(1):908–920. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/26895293.2022.2112766>.
- 25) Albakry Z, Karrar E, Ahmed IAM, Oz EA, Proestos C, Sheikha AFE, et al. Nutritional Composition and Volatile Compounds of Black Cumin (*Nigella sativa* L.) Seed, Fatty Acid Composition and Tocopherols, Polyphenols, and Antioxidant Activity of Its Essential Oil. *Horticulturae*. 2022;8(7):575. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae8070575>.
- 26) Ndirangu EG, Opiyo SA, Mw N. Chemical composition and repellency of *Nigella sativa* L. seed essential oil against *Anopheles gambiae* sensu stricto. *Trends in Phytochemical Research (TPR)*. 2020;4(2):77–84. Available from: https://tpr.shahrood.iau.ir/article_672458.html.
- 27) Rostaei M, Fallah S, Lorigooini Z, Surki AA. Crop productivity and chemical compositions of black cumin essential oil in sole crop and intercropped with soybean under contrasting fertilization. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2018;125:622–629. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2018.09.044>.
- 28) Benelli G, Pavea R, Petrelli R, Cappellacci L, Santini G, Fiorini D, et al. The essential oil from industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) by-products as an effective tool for insect pest management in organic crops. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2018;122:308–315. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2018.05.032>.
- 29) Alfred TN, Ceylan O, Godloves CF, Arab Y, Duru ME, Ozturk M. Antimicrobial, antibiofilm, anti-quorum sensing and motility inhibition activities of essential oil from seeds of food spice *Xylocopa aethiopica* (Dunal) A. Rich. on some pathogenic bacteria. *Research Journal of Biotechnology*. 2021;16(6):68–76. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1420-3049/27/15/4872/htm>.
- 30) Maurya AK, Sharma A, Mukhia S, Rani D, Kumar AD, Kumar RD, et al. Essential Oil Composition, In Vitro Biological Activities and Safety Evaluation of Cultivated *Hedychium spicatum* Seeds. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022;84(3):783–790. Available from: https://tpr.shahrood.iau.ir/article_672458.html.